

The Catechins of the Cutch-producing Acacias.

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Singh (*Indian Forest Memoirs*, 1905, 1, 34) was the first to draw attention to the differences in the melting points of catechin from cutch (m.p. 195-198°), and kheersal (m.p. 225-230°), the catechin found in the heart-wood of *Acacia Catechu*. Sixteen years later Freudenberg and Purrmann (*Annalen*, 1924, 437, 278) showed that the heart-wood of *A. Catechu* contained mainly *l*-epicatechin (m.p. 230°), and also some *dl*-catechin (m.p. 212°). According to Freudenberg and Purrmann *l*-epicatechin undergoes epimerisation and racemisation, during the manufacture of cutch, *dl*-catechin (m.p. 212°) being produced. From nearly thirty years' experience with catechin the present writer is inclined to believe that the variations between Singh's melting points and those given by Freudenberg and Purrmann for the catechin found in the wood and that in the cutch, are within the limits of experimental error, an opinion which would appear to be corroborated by the variation in melting points of *dl*-catechin alone—216-18°, 214-16°, 204-5°, 212-14°, and 212°, recorded by Freudenberg and his collaborators. The melting points of the different catechins are greatly affected by moisture—a point which has been particularly emphasised in the case of gambier-catechin (see Kostanecki and Tambor, *Ber.*, 1902, 35, 1867; Clauser, *ibid.*, 1903, 36, 101; Perkin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 398) which melts at 96°, 175-77°, and 210° respectively, these variations being due to the water of crystallisation. For this reason the author prefers the different penta-acetyl derivatives, for identification purposes as these crystallise with ease from alcohol and have constant melting points. In view of these considerations no doubt remains that to Singh belongs the credit of having discovered the native catechin of *A. Catechu*.

According to Freudenberg and Purrmann the first stage in the conversion of kheersal (mainly *l*-epicatechin) into *dl*-catechin (known in the literature as acacatechin), consists in the epimerisation of *l*-epicatechin to *l*-catechin which is followed by the second stage, namely, the racemisation of *l*-catechin to *dl*-catechin (acacatechin).

On heating an aqueous solution of *l*-epicatechin under pressure Freudenberg and Purrmann obtained a mixture of four catechins, namely, *l*-epicatechin, *l*-catechin, *dl*-epicatechin, and *dl*-catechin; and further, they demonstrated that the reaction is reversible, since, starting out from *l*-catechin and working under the same conditions, they obtained *l*-catechin, *l*-epicatechin, *dl*-catechin, *dl*-epicatechin.

A clear understanding of these reactions, the extent to which they take place, possible variations of yields, and of the factors controlling these, is obviously fundamental to the chemistry of catech, and at the writer's request therefore Miss Edith O. Hazelton repeated Freudenberg's experiment on a large scale, with the single difference that whereas Freudenberg and Purrmann had started from *l*-catechin or *l*-epicatechin respectively, and obtained a mixture of four catechins, Miss Hazelton started from *dl*-catechin, which, on epimerisation could only lead to a mixture of two catechins, namely, *dl*-catechin and *dl*-epicatechin.

The collective evidence of Miss Hazelton's experiments, full details of which are given in the experimental part of this paper, revealed however no trace of epimerised catechin. Furthermore simple considerations of Freudenberg and Purrmann's discovery in *A. Catechu* of *dl*-catechin, as well as *l*-epicatechin, the main constituent of the heart-wood suggest only one explanation, which is hard to realise, namely, that in the plant, *l*-epicatechin is epimerised, as well as racemised, at the exclusion of *dl*-epicatechin leading to the production of *dl*-catechin. At one time during the progress of the present investigation it was thought that evidence had accumulated showing the presence of *dl*-epicatechin in the wood, since *three* catechins were found in the heart-wood, namely, α -catechin (m.p. 204-5°), β -catechin (m.p. 230°) and γ -catechin (m.p. 226-8°), yielding the corresponding penta-acetyl derivatives, having melting points 160°, 151°, and 171° respectively. However subsequent work has shown that only two of these catechins are stereoisomers, that is to say β -catechin, which is laevo-rotatory, can be racemised to α -catechin, *vis.*, *acacatechin* (Nierenstein, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 114) whereas γ -catechin, which is also laevo-rotatory, is a structural isomer of α - and β -catechin, since it can be racemised to *isoacacatechin* (Nierenstein, *Ber.*, 1923, 56, 1877). The following names have therefore been provisionally assigned to these three catechins, *dl*-*acacatechin* (m.p. 204-5°; acetyl derivative, m.p. 160°), *l*-*acacatechin* (m.p. 230°; acetyl derivative, m.p. 151°), and *l*-*isoacacatechin*

(m.p. 226-8°; acetyl derivative, m.p. 171°). The constitution of acocatechin is shown in formula I, whereas formula II represents the constitution of isocatechin.

(I)

(II)

The results obtained in this laboratory go to show that—
 (1) During the manufacture of cutch the greater part of the catechin is destroyed, thus the ethyl acetate extracts obtained on exhaustive extraction of the heart-wood as well as of the cutches prepared from the same wood, are found to give the following comparative catechin values on exhaustive extraction with ether:

Catechin content.

	Wood.	Cutch.
<i>Acacia Catechu</i> , Log A.	58·00%	14·75%
<i>Acacia Catechu</i> , Log B.	62·40%	10·40%
<i>Acacia Catechu</i> , Log C.	70·00%	32·00%
<i>Acacia Sundra</i> .	61·00%	38·30%
<i>Acacia Catechuoides</i> .	59·00%	25·10%

(2) Racemisation of the two optically active catechins takes place to some extent, but is erratic, and far from being complete. This is shown in the following summary:—

	Heart-wood.			Cutch.		
	<i>dl</i> -Aca-catechin.	<i>l</i> -Aca-catechin.	<i>l</i> -isoAca-catechin.	<i>dl</i> -Aca-catechin.	<i>l</i> -Aca-catechin.	<i>l</i> -isoAca-catechin.
<i>Acacia Catechu</i> , Log A.	13·84%	51·70%	32·98%	77·00%	—	23·00%
<i>Acacia Catechu</i> , Log B.	13·57%	75·98%	9·45%	51·2%	—	48·60%
<i>Acacia Catechu</i> , Log C.	22·40%	74·20%	3·40%	13·40%	72·10%	14·50%
<i>Acacia Sundra</i>	8·10%	94·30%	2·60%	—	100·0%	—
<i>Acacia Catechuoides</i>	22·70%	73·90%	3·40%	45·90%	48·40%	4·1%

It will be realised that it is quite impossible to generalise from these results, or to use them in support of any theory of the mechanism of cutch production from catechin. Only a large number of experiments, preferably carried out in India, will elucidate the points raised by this preliminary work.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The wood as well as the cutches was exhaustively extracted with ethyl acetate in a large Soxhlet apparatus. The cutches were finely powdered, passed through a 30-sieve and mixed with ten times their own weight of white sand.* The ethyl acetate extracts were evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure and the remaining solid powdered and again mixed with ten times its own weight of sand. It was then fractionally extracted in a Soxhlet apparatus with ether free from alcohol. The first fraction was obtained after thirty minutes' extraction and the time of extraction increased for each subsequent fraction. Extraction was continued until no solid was obtained on evaporation of the ether. The average time of extraction totalled 200 hours. The solids obtained on evaporation of the ether were dissolved in hot water slightly acidulated with acetic acid (see Nierenstein, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 609) and the solid collected after standing for twenty-four hours. The catechin fractions thus obtained were again recrystallised from water and the weight of each fraction and its melting point recorded after standing in a vacuum desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid for 3-5 days. Each fraction was then acetylated by heating with acetic anhydride and the solid obtained on precipitation with water crystallised from alcohol and a few drops of acetone. The melting point and the mixed melting point with specially purified authentic specimens were recorded. The filtrates of the different fractions were all mixed together, and evaporated by standing over concentrated sulphuric acid, the solid thus obtained was powdered and mixed with sand, and again fractionally extracted with ether, and examined in the manner described above, the aqueous filtrates of these second fractions being solidified and examined in the same way. It was generally found that these third solids contained little or no catechin.

* The sand used was at first treated with a dilute hydrochloric acid, then washed with water, alcohol and ether. It was then dried at 100° and powdered.

The results obtained after this somewhat lengthy process have already been summarised in the introduction, and although they did not yield data which could lend themselves to the development of a theory as to the fate of catechin during the manufacture of cutch they may serve as a useful basis for other workers in this field.

As regards Miss Hazelton's results, which are summarised in the accompanying table, they were obtained as follows:—100 g. *dl*-catechin (m.p. 204-5°; acetyl derivative, m.p. 100°) were heated under pressure according to the conditions laid down by Freudenberg and Parmann for the epimerisation of *l*-epicatechin. The crystalline remaining catechin was then filtered off and dried, the mother liquor being carefully evaporated to a syrupy solution, when no further catechin crystallised out. The syrup was left to dry over sulphuric acid till it formed a solid. The solid obtained was powdered, and thoroughly mixed with the crystalline catechin which had been recovered, this mixture was then put through a 30-sieve, and left to dry in a desiccator over sulphuric acid for about a week. 30 G. of the cutch produced were examined in the manner already described.

The accompanying tables have been reproduced from the laboratory book of Miss Hazelton, who died at a very early age.

In conclusion, the author's thanks are due to the authorities of the Forest Research Institute at Dehra Dun, for their generosity in supplying the necessary material for this investigation.

TABLE I.
Bihexal Fractionation of Pure Anacatechin which has been heated under pressure. Fractions called "O"

No.	Time, (hrs.)	Weight of dish (g.)	Weight of residue and dish (g.)	Weight of glass. and watch glass (g.)	Wt. of catechin (g.)	Total weight of catechin (g.)	Melting point.	Acetyl derivative m.p.	Recryst. m.p.	Mixed m.p.
1	1	28.00	31.00	3.00	4.20	0.25	3.25	Sinters strongly at 160°; m.p. 200-202°	160°	160°
2	1½	34.80	38.10	3.30	5.00	1.00	4.30	204-205°	160°	160°
3	1½	30.95	33.70	2.75	6.80	0.80	3.55	Sinters strongly at 160°; m.p. 201-203°	160°	160°
4	3	34.30	36.90	2.60	7.75	2.20	4.80	202-204°	155-157°	160°
5	4½	28.00	30.10	2.10	11.20	2.20	4.80	202-204°	160°	160°
6	3½	34.80	41.10	6.30	13.70	2.70	9.00	200-203°	160°	160°
7	6	30.95	32.50	1.55	9.30	1.50	3.05	198-202°	160°	160°
8	6	34.30	35.05	0.75	13.10	1.95	2.70	204-206°	160°	160°
9	4½	34.80	36.30	0.40	14.80	1.65	2.05	208-208°	160°	160°
10	8	28.00	28.05	0.05	9.85	0.95	1.00	190-196°	160°	160°
11	9	30.95	31.05	0.10	5.00	0.90	1.00	198-200°	160°	160°
12	9	28.00	28.10	0.10	2.75	0.85	0.90	204-205°	160°	160°
13	13	30.95	31.00	0.05	10.05	0.45	0.50	203-205°	160°	160°
14	11	30.95	31.10	0.15	11.80	0.65	0.80	208-204°	160°	160°
15	14	28.00	28.05	0.05	7.30	0.35	0.40	202-204°	160°	160°
16	13	30.95	31.00	0.05	3.40	0.40	0.45	201-203°	160°	160°
17	14	36.90	36.60	0.10	11.00	0.65	0.75	202-203°	160°	160°
18	26½	33.45	33.50	0.05	No catechin	0.05	0.05	160°	160°	160°
Total 158½				23.45		19.40	43.85			

2nd crystals to be found in table II.

TABLE II.

2nd Crystals C1A, etc.

No.	Wt. of watch glass (g.)	Wt. of catechin and watch glass(g.)	catechin (g.)	Melting point.	Acetyl derivative M.p.	Recrys. m.p.	Mixed m.p.
1A	7.85	8.40	0.55	160-165°	159-160°	160°	160°
2A	8.05	8.50	0.45	100-110°	110-125°, 150-158°	155-156°	155-160°
2A	9.80	10.00	0.20	157-160°	160°	...	160°
4A	2.80	3.90	0.10	202-204°	160°	...	160°
5A	1.45	1.55	0.10	199-200°	160°	...	160°
6A	2.95	3.10	0.15	160-163°	160°	...	160°
7A	No second crystals						
8A	1.50	1.60	0.10	198-200°	160°	...	160°
9A	1.65	1.75	0.10	195-198°	160°	...	160°
10A	9.70	9.80	0.10	194-198°	160°	...	160°
11A	7.85	7.95	0.10	190-196°	160°	...	160°
15A	9.60	9.85	0.25	201-203°	160°	...	160°
Residues							
6 hrs.	5.05	5.35	0.30	105-120°	157-160°	160°	160°
15 hrs.	No catechin						
	Total		2.50				
	Total catechin		19.40	Total extract 4.285			
			2.50	2.20			
				45.05 g. = 90.1%.			
				21.90 g. = 49.80%.			

49.80% catechin recovered and the whole of this amount was unchanged catechin. No trace of epimerised substance.

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